

CORRELATION OF PLASTICS AND GFRP IMPACT STRENGTHS
OBTAINED BY CONVENTIONAL PENDULUM TYPE AND
LINEAR PROBE TYPE IMPACT TESTING MACHINES

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ABSTRACT

In order to check the correlation of material impact strengths obtained by a conventional pendulum type and a linear probe type impact testing machine, Izod impact tests of Polybutylene Terephthalate and Glass Fiber Reinforced Polybutylene Terephthalate were carried. From those test results, it was found that a very good correlation holds between the data by two different type impact testing machines for the case of impact speed of 3.5 m/s. Discussions and problem points are also presented.

INTRODUCTION

Izod and Charpy impact strengths by conventional pendulum type impact testing machines have been widely used for evaluation of material properties for linear impact. The impactor performs a circular motion as pendulum, whereas its impact data have been evaluated as linear impact data so far. But if a linearly moving impactor is used, the impact strength may be or not different from that of pendulum type machine?

In order to clarify this point, it needs to carry out impact tests by linearly moving impactor as well as Izod or Charpy pendulum impactor, using test specimens of the same kind of material having the same geometry under the same fixing conditions.

In the present paper, taking up Izod test as the evaluation base, the comparison tests by a linear probe impact testing machine-RIT 8000 made by Rheometrics Inc., USA and a conventional pendulum type impact testing machine made by TOYO-SEIKI Company, Japan, were conducted, using PBT (Polybutylene Terephthalate) and GF/PBT (Glas Fiber Reinforced PBT) as test specimen materials. The test method of JIS(Japan Industrial Standard) K-7110 which corresponds to ASTM-D256) was adopted for all tests. The correlation of test data obtained by both methods was investigated.

Discussions and problem points were also presented.

MATERIALS AND TEST METHOD

Testing Materials and Processing

As the impact test materials, three kinds of TORAY-PBT designated as PBT-1, PBT-2 and PBT-3 and three kinds of GF/PBT designated as GF/PBT-A, GF/PBT-B and GF/PBT-C were used.

PBT-1 is PBT specimen taken as reference one, PBT-2 a rubber-modified high impact strength PBT and PBT-3 a rubber-modified very high impact strength PBT, respectively.

GF/PBT-A, GF/PBT-B and GF/PBT-C are Glas Fiber Reinforced normal PBT, Glass Fiber reinforced rubber-modified high impact strength PBT and Glass Fiber reinforced rubber-modified very high impact strength PBT, respectively. The matrix materials of these composites: PBT-A, -B and -C are slightly different from PBT-1, -2 and -3, respectively.

Glas Fiber of 13 μ diameter and aspect ratio of 20 was used.

Volume fraction of Glass Fiber was 17 %.

Processing and Geometry of Test Specimen

TABLE 1 and Figure 1 show the processing conditions of test specimen materials and geometry of test specimen, respectively.

Test specimens having two kinds of width 12.7 mm and 3.18 mm were fabricated. V-notch of specimens of 12.7 mm width was made by machining and that of 3.18 mm width specimens was made by molding with metal molds. The other dimensions of the latter specimens were the same as those of the former specimens. As seen in Figure 1, notch bottom radius, depth of V-notch and V-notch angle were 0.25 mm, 2.54 mm and 45 degree, respectively. Height of acting position of impact load measured from V-notch was 22.0 mm.

TABLE 1
Test specimen processing conditions

Item		Unreinforced PBT	GF/PBT	Unreinforced Nylon
Machine		TOSHIBA IS-50AM (inline screw type)		
Metal Mold		1/2 in width Izod and 1/8 in width mold notch Izod specimen		
Temperature on mold surface	°C	80	80	80
Temperature of Cylinder	°C	250	260	280
Injection Pressure	kgf/cm ²	LLP+5	LLP+10	LLP+20
Process cycle (Injection/Cooling)	sec	15/20	15/15	18/17

LLP = Lower Limit Pressure: 35 for PBT-1; 40 for GF/PBT

Figure 1. Izod test specimen geometry

Testing Machines and Test Conditions

Testing Machines

RIT-8000 Linear Impact Testing Machine(LITM) was used for linear impact test. Figure 2 shows its linear impact probe and specimen attachment device.[1]

Load cell and impact edge were installed at the end of linear probe. The shape of impact edge was made similarly to that of Pendulum type Impact

Testing Machine (PITM).

Load cell capacity was ca 500 kgf(1000lbs).

Attachment device of test specimen was designed similarly to PITM as far as possible as seen in Figure 2.

As a pendulum type impact machine (PITM), Izod testing machine made by TOYO-SEIKI Inc. was used, whose hammer capacity was 4.00 Nm (3 ft-lb) for specimen PBT-3 and 1.33 Nm (1 ft-lb) for the other specimens.

Figure 2. Impact edge fixed to RIT-8000 impact probe and attachment of test specimen to loading plate.

Test Condition

The following test conditions were adopted for all specimens:

- (1) Impact speed = 3.5 m/s ($\pm 5\%$),
 - (2) Temperature = 23°C ($\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$),
 - (3) Relative humidity = 50% ($\pm 5\%$),
- commonly for LITM and PITM.

- (4) Number of test specimen = 10~15 for LITM each specimen,
= 10 for PITM each specimen.

All tests were carried out in such manner that specimen V-notch lies in the same side as impact load side. In tests by LITM, impact load and displacement of impact edge and work done by linear probe were autographed. In the case of PITM, only the work done was measured.

TEST RESULTS

Test results are shown in TABLE 2 and 3, Figure 3 to 6. All of Figures are test results obtained by LITM.

Fundamental Properties of Specimen Materials

TABLE 2 shows the fundamental properties of PBT and GF/PBT materials. In order to search high impact strength materials, rubber-modified PBT were also investigated.[2]

Impact Test Data by LITM

Figure 3 shows the typical relationships of impact load P vs displacement δ for PBT-1,-2 and -3. In this Figure, for example, with regard to PBT-3 graph, the designations for typical three points on the graph are made. They are Maximum Load Point where P becomes maximum, Break Point where is the lowest foot point of the first peak of P - δ graph, and Final Point where impact finishes. These designations are used in TABLE 3.

TABLE 2
Fundamental properties of specimen materials

Specimen Materials	Substance	Properties				Notched TP	
		σ_t kgf/mm ²	Elongation %	E_b kgf/mm ²	Notchless IS kgf.cm cm ²	Width 12.7mm V-mach.	Width 3.18mm Mold.N.
PBT-1	standard	5.70	100	250	NB	o	o
PBT-2	HI-RM	4.90	150	230	NB	o	-
PBT-3	VHI-RM	3.75	250	170	NB	o	-
GF/PBT A	GF-Reinforced $V_f=17\%$	14.00	4	900	55	o	o
GF/PBT B	GF-RM-HI $V_f=17\%$	12.50	5	820	75	-	o
GF/PBT C	GF-RM-VHI $V_f=17\%$	11.20	5	720	105	-	o
Nylon	Nylon-66	8.00	110	290	NB	o	-

σ_t = Tensile strength,
 E_b = Flexural modulus,
IS = Impact Strength,
TP = Test Piece,

HI = High Impact,
RM = Rubber Modified,
VHI = Very High Impact,
V-mach. = Machined V-notch,
Mold.N. = Molded V-notch.

Impact strength IS is given by U/A where A is the cross sectional area of the notch bottom section of test specimen and U is the value of work done at Break Point or Final Point.

Figure 3 to 6 represent $P \sim \delta$ and $U \sim \delta$ plots for PBT-1,2,3 and GF/PBT-A, B and C measured by LITM. Figure 5 and 6 for GF/PBT also show the repeatability of test results. [1]

Impact Data by PITM

Impact test data by PITM show in TABLE 2 and 3. In these tests, only the total energy until Final Point was measured.

TABLE 3
Impact strengths obtained by pendulum type and linear probe type (RIT-8000) impact testing machine

Material	b Width of test piece mm	IS Impact Strength by Pendulum Type kgf.cm/cm ²	IS by Linear Probe Type--RIT-8000					
			Max.Load Point		Break Point		Final Point	
			Displacement mm	Load kgf	Displacement mm	IS kgf.cm/cm ²	Displacement mm	IS kgf.cm/cm ²
PBT-1	12.7	3.6 (s=0.17)	1.1	37.7	2.4	2.9 (s=0.24)	21.0	3.3 (s=0.35)
PBT-2	12.7	6.2 (s=1.7)	1.3	58.3	2.5	5.5 (s=0.47)	16.0	6.2 (s=0.59)
PBT-3	12.7	60 (s=1.7)	4.5	90.8	15.0	54 (s=2.0)	22.1	58 (s=2.6)
GF/PBT A	12.7	8.9 (s=0.50)	0.8	66.3	3.9	6.9 (s=0.45)	21.5	8.3 (s=0.47)
Nylon 66	12.7	5.3 (s=0.40)	1.3	67.3	2.9	4.0 (s=0.48)	21.7	4.8 (s=0.46)
PBT-1	3.18	4.8 (s=0.29)	0.4	15.3	1.9	3.3 (s=0.25)	7.4	4.2 (s=0.36)
GF/PBT A	3.18	9.1 (s=0.26)	0.8	36.7	1.9	10.0 (s=0.90)	7.5	11.1 (s=1.22)
GF/PBT B	3.18	13.0 (s=0.65)	1.2	38.8	2.1	10.4 (s=0.68)	9.2	13.3 (s=1.09)
GF/PBT C	3.18	16.9 (s=0.50)	1.5	42.8	2.5	14.1 (s=0.74)	8.4	16.8 (s=1.47)

IS = Impact Strength, s = Standard deviation.

Break Point = Point passed down the first peak of load vs displacement curve,

Final Point = Point corresponding to the maximum absorbed energy.

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 3, 4 and 5
Impact Load P vs Displacement δ and Work Done U vs Displacement δ Graphs for PBT and GF/PBT by LITM.

Figure 6 Impact Load p vs Displacement δ and Work Done U vs Displacement δ Graph for GF/PBT-B and C by LITM.

DISCUSSION

Correlation between Impact Strengths obtained by LITM and PITM

In the test by PITM, only total work done was measured. Hence, the comparison of impact strengths referred to total work done was possible. From the comparison of the 3rd and last column data of TABLE 3 for impact speed of 3.5m/s and specimen width of 12.7 and 3.18 mm, it was found that both data show very good coincidence over wide range of impact strength. Consideration on Fracture Energy

In conventional impact tests, only total work done during impact is measured and impact strength is calculated. Total work done U consists of U_0 , which is necessary to cause real fracture only, and the residual work ΔU . If ΔU is negligible small and U_0 would be assumed to be nearly equal to U_{BP} (work done until "Break Point"), the impact strength U_{BP}/A becomes the values of the 7th column of TABLE 3. These values are 10 to 15% smaller than the impact strengths calculated from the total work done. Such modification seems to be necessary for conventional impact test result.

Other Findings

It was also found that the specimen size gives remarkable effect on impact strength and that rubber-modification and GF reinforcing have shown linearly additive effectiveness on impact strength.

CONCLUSION

In order to study the correlation between the impact strengths which obtained by using linear probe type impact testing machine(RIT-8000) and conventional pendulum type impact testing machine, impact tests were done, using Izod type test specimens made of PBT and GF/PBT under the standard condition. And impact load was applied to the V-notch side of test specimen at impact speed of 3.5 m/s.

From the comparison of data by both machines, it was confirmed that there exists a good correlation between them, as far as the impact strength values are calculated from the total work done.

It will be future problems to make clear true fracture energy, investigate the effect of impact speed on impact behaviours and computational approach.[3,4]

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